

**Undergraduate Research at San Jac: A High-Impact Practical Case at a Two-Year
Institution**

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Abstract

This work presents a case study of undergraduate research at San Jacinto College as an example of a high-impact practice. Two-year institutions often face obstacles such as limited funding, short student enrollment periods, and little dedicated research space. Even with these challenges, students and faculty at San Jacinto College have created opportunities that connect class learning with real research. Two projects are highlighted. The first is atmospheric monitoring carried out with NASA's Pandora spectrometer network. This project has been successful in identifying patterns in NO₂ and O₃ levels, both of which are considered by the EPA as atmospheric pollutants. The second project examines shoreline change using numerical methods. Here, a relatively new method of mitigating beach erosion is explored using mega-nourishments (MNs), where a large volume of sand is placed at a single nourishment site, and the sediment is redistributed to nearby beaches via natural processes. MN modeling research here explores the effects of various conditions (e.g., wave conditions, topographic parameters, etc.) on hypothetical MN evolution to better understand how prospective MN projects may evolve. Both research efforts give students experience in handling data, applying research tools, and presenting their results in novel research projects. Since these research activities began in 2018, students have produced and presented more than 50 posters and contributed to several peer-reviewed publications. At the same time, the projects contributed to wider conversations in science and the local community.

Keywords: undergraduate research, high-impact practice, San Jacinto College, student learning, case study

Undergraduate Research at San Jac: A High-Impact Practical Case at a Two-Year Institution

Undergraduate research is considered a high-impact practice because it helps students keep learning beyond the classroom and connect their studies to real-world applications (Kuh, 2008). At four-year universities, undergraduate research has been part of academic programs for many years. Two-year colleges face several barriers when trying to build a research culture. Funding is limited, and resources are often scarce. Most students are at the institution for only two years, and many do not start research until their last semester. This short time frame makes it difficult to keep projects going. Research infrastructure in a two-year institution is also generally limited. Space for research (e.g., laboratories and their required equipment) is hard to find, as most space is dedicated to teaching endeavors. Faculty face similar limitations as no time is officially set aside for research (SJC, 2020). The current faculty workload is mostly teaching (70%) with smaller portions for professional development and service (15% each). As a result, research must be carried out in addition to regular teaching and service duties.

Despite these barriers, San Jacinto College (SJC) has developed a growing research culture since 2018. This paper highlights two projects that illustrate this work. One involves the use of NASA's Pandora spectrometer to monitor air quality in addition to the satellite data and EPA ground-based data. The other uses numerical modeling to study shoreline change. These projects are presented as a case study of how a two-year college can create and sustain research under limited conditions. Since the research efforts started in 2018, students have conducted novel research, presented more than 50 posters, and have also been part of several peer-reviewed papers. These projects have also opened space for conversations in science and in the local community. At the same time, the projects contributed to wider conversations in science and the

local community. This paper outlines how these initiatives provide students with new skills, allow faculty to remain engaged in scholarship, and increase institutional visibility. The guiding question is, “How can community colleges create meaningful undergraduate research and overcome the barriers they face?” Some examples of student-produced research are also presented to highlight the quality of their work.

Framework or Theoretical Perspective

Previous studies have reported the positive impact of undergraduate research experience in attracting more students to science, technology, engineering, and mathematics (STEM) fields. For example, Russell et al. (2007) found that students in undergraduate research often reported greater interest in STEM careers. They also described improved understanding of the research process, stronger confidence, and clearer expectations about graduate school. Meselhe et al. (2025) noted that mentoring plays an important role in building confidence and research identity. Tsang et al. (2024) and Linn et al. (2015) showed that collaboration with faculty can promote deeper learning and personal growth. Equity impact has also been well-documented as participation in undergraduate research reduces graduation gaps for underrepresented minority students (Carpi et al., 2017). At Hispanic-serving institutions such as SJC, research experiences have been shown to improve career awareness, confidence, and students’ sense of belonging in STEM (Hernandez et al., 2018). Together, these studies emphasize why the San Jacinto College projects are significant. They suggest that undergraduate research, even at the community college level, can create valuable outcomes for students, faculty, and the institution.

Methodology

While San Jacinto College faculty have been performing research for many years, the research projects outlined here started in 2018. The research model involves a faculty member

(in the sciences in this case) mentoring one or more students through a complete research project, similar to an advisor-student relationship in graduate school. The goal is to give SJC students an experience similar to that of a graduate-level science thesis but on a smaller scale. Students are typically recruited from classes taught by the faculty (e.g., College Physics I & II and University Physics I & II). Students are expected to commit to at least one full semester of conducting research. The research project is expected to produce at least one deliverable, examples of which are a poster presentation (usually at a conference or symposium), a written thesis, or co-authorship in a peer-reviewed journal article (preferably all the above). Students perform these research projects in addition to their regular studies. Students generally are expected to spend their own time conducting research, often having to additionally manage academic, professional, and personal schedules. While they do not receive course credit for their projects at present, students are encouraged to prominently mention their research experiences on their résumés and/or curriculum vitae. Students also have the option to continue their research beyond the first semester and/or into the summer sessions if their schedule allows. Note that students must be active SJC students in order to participate in research, but they are not required to pay additional tuition or fees for the experience.

Research spaces are established by the administration of the Department of Physical Sciences (Astronomy, Chemistry, Geology, and Physics) from rooms available to the department. The current spaces available are the Undergraduate Research Center (housing general research equipment, e.g., chemistry equipment) and the Computational Undergraduate Research Center (housing computing resources). The college does not currently have dedicated funding for research equipment, and as such, equipment is typically procured via external grants. For example, the Pandora spectrometer equipment was funded using the Higher Education

Emergency Relief Fund from the U.S. Department of Education, and the computing equipment for numerical modeling was purchased using funding from the Title III STEM Grant awarded by the U.S. Department of Energy for Hispanic Serving Institutions (SJC, 2021).

Two major research initiatives have been successfully implemented using this research scheme: the Pandora Spectrometer Project and the Shoreline Numerical Modeling Project. Detailed descriptions of these projects are below. These descriptions are included to showcase the quality level of research being performed by the students.

Pandora Spectrometer Project

This study used the observations from the Pandora Spectrometer System installed at San Jacinto College South Campus in November 2023 (as shown in Figure 1). The instrument measures solar radiation in the ultraviolet and visible range (280–525 nm) and provides total atmospheric column and vertically resolved values of gases such as ozone (O₃) and nitrogen dioxide (NO₂). The optical head tracks the sun during the day, and the collected light is passed through a fiber-optic cable into a local computer, where the data are saved before being uploaded to the Pandonia Global Network (PGN).

PGN began in 2019 as a joint effort between NASA and the European Space Agency. It now includes more than 165 monitoring sites in over 35 countries. The network applies the same calibration, processing, and archiving methods at each site so that measurements can be compared across locations. San Jacinto College is the first community college to operate a Pandora instrument and contribute to this global system.

For this project, Pandora retrievals collected from January to June 2024 were examined. The files were downloaded from the San Jacinto College directory on the PGN portal. The raw

data was processed with Python scripts to obtain daily and weekly averages. Then, statistical methods are used to calculate monthly means and create box-and-whisker plots.

The analysis examined both seasonal and weekly changes in O_3 and NO_2 . The monthly averages showed how levels varied with the season, while weekday–weekend comparisons pointed to the impact of traffic and industrial activity. Together, these results helped separate natural variation in the atmosphere from changes linked to human activity.

Figure 1: Pandora spectrometer located on the rooftop of San Jacinto College S-1 Building (South Campus) in November of 2023. At the top, there is a long black tube called the observer that tracks the sun during the day. This measures different trace gases using a 280-525 nm spectral range. It sends this data through a fiber optic cable into a local computer, where it gets stored and uploaded to the PGN network.

Shoreline Numerical Modeling Project

This project examines efforts to mitigate beach erosion. Many U.S. beaches are actively eroding largely due to sediment transport caused by wave action. Traditionally, this has been combated by artificially transporting additional sand to eroded beaches through a process called beach nourishment. However, this method of preservation is short-term, and repetitive nourishments are costly. A potential solution to this problem is a mega-nourishment (MN), where a large amount of sand is placed in one location (de Schipper et al., 2016; Figure 2). This

sediment is then redistributed via natural processes (e.g., wave action) to nearby beaches, thus nourishing a large beach area with a single project. To date, there have been no MNs constructed in the U.S., and thus numerical models must be used to investigate how hypothetical U.S. MNs may evolve.

Figure 2. Aerial photograph of the Sand Engine (*Zandmotor*) on the Dutch coast, the first mega-nourishment ever constructed. This shows the mega-nourishment after roughly two years of evolution. Its shoreline shape (roughly Gaussian) and aspect parameters are similar to those of hypothetical MNs described here. Photo courtesy of Dutch Ministry of Infrastructure and the Environment.

Undergraduate students undertaking this research use the Coastline Evolution Model (Ashton et al., 2001; Ashton & Murray, 2006a, 2006b), MATLAB version (Whitley, 2022), to simulate the change in the shape of the nourishment over time. CEM is described in detail in Ashton and Murray (2006a, 2006b) and Whitley et al. (2021), so only key points are shown here. The model lays out the beach area in a grid simulating land cells (full of sediment), ocean cells (with no sediment), and beach (shoreline) cells (partially full of sediment), and accounts for the position of the beach cells to simulate the shoreline (as shown in Figure 3). The model simulates

the shoreline's evolution by iteratively calculating the amount of sediment (flux) that is transported laterally (longshore) across beach cell boundaries due to wave action. Sediment fluxes (Q_s) across cell boundaries are calculated every time step via the CERC Equation (Rosati et al., 2002):

$$Q_s = K_1 \left(\frac{\rho \sqrt{g}}{16\gamma^2(\rho_s - \rho)(1 - p_s)} \right) H_b^{\frac{5}{2}} \sin(2\alpha_b), \quad (1)$$

where H_b is the water wave height when breaking, α_b is the breaking wave angle (relative to the shoreline), ρ is the water density, g is the acceleration due to gravity, ρ_s is the sediment density, K_1 is the empirical proportionality coefficient, p_s is the sediment porosity, and γ is the breaker index (ratio of H_b to the water depth at breaking). The change in the fractional amount of sediment in each cell (ΔF , calculated every time step) is given by:

$$\Delta F = \frac{(Q_{in} - Q_{out})}{(d_c + d_b)W^2}, \quad (2)$$

where W is the width of the cell (generally 25 m here), Q_{in} and Q_{out} are the Q_s values transported into and out of a cell respectively, d_c is the maximum water depth where sediment can be transported (also known as the depth of closure), and d_b is the height of the beach berm above mean sea level (see Figure 3b). The amount of Q_s entering and leaving a beach cell is the critical driver in shoreline change. When more sediment enters a beach cell than is being transported out, that cell experiences accretion (shoreline extension). Consequently, when there is a greater Q_s leaving a cell than entering, that beach cell experiences erosion (shoreline retreat). Note that the model assumes that sediment is being transported evenly across the subaerial (above water) and subaqueous (below water) shoreface out to the depth of closure d_c .

Figure 3. (a) Schematic of the Coastline Evolution Model (CEM). The model lays out the beach, land, and ocean areas in a cellular grid. The coastline (represented by the red line) is accounted for via the amount of sediment in the beach cells. The numerical model takes offshore wave information (wave direction) and numerically transforms that information into breaking wave information. From the breaking wave information, sediment transport (flux, Q_s) across cell boundaries can be calculated. The amount of sediment entering and leaving a cell determines if each cell experiences coastal erosion or accretion, resulting in coastline change. (b) Cross-shore profile of the model showing the beach berm, shoreface, and continental shelf. The model assumes that sediment is transported evenly over the shoreface from the top of the berm down to a depth d_c .

The model is driven by offshore wave information that is transformed numerically into breaking wave information for use in (1). The wave transformation process (details in Whitley, 2014 and Whitley, 2022) accounts for wave refraction and shoaling via linear wave theory (i.e., Snell's Law). As a result, CEM's coastline morphology is extremely sensitive to the offshore wave climate input. CEM uses a probability distribution function (PDF) to determine offshore angle (α_0) relative to shore-normal for each time step in the model (for details on PDF theory, see Ashton & Murray, 2006b). For this research, the PDF is controlled by two variables: asymmetry (A), the fraction of waves approaching from the left of the domain, and the "highness" (U), the fraction of offshore waves approaching the coast from a high angle ($\alpha_0 \geq 45^\circ$). Theoretically, A should control the dominant direction of sediment transport (left/right) while U should control how quickly shoreline features (like an MN bump) either grow or diffuse (Falqués, 2003; Ashton & Murray, 2006a; 2006b). It should also be noted that CEM has wave

shadowing algorithms where a large shoreline formation (such as an MN) can block highly oblique waves approaching the shore. This results in wave shadow zones (as shown in Figure 3a) downdrift of an MN that effectively blocks wave action in the shadowed regions. The model assumes all cross-shore sediment transport (CST) is negligible and only accounts for longshore sediment transport (LST).

For these undergraduate studies, CEM simulates hypothetical MNs evolution over 25 to 100 years in novel studies. The MN's initial shoreline is a Gaussian-shaped peninsula (similar to that in Figure 2), and the nourishment's volume is ~ 17.5 million m^3 of sediment. It has a cross-shore length of ~ 1 km and a longshore (beach-long) footprint of ~ 5 km. As wave climate has a considerable effect on MN evolution, a variety of wave climates are tested by changing the PDF variables A and U . Two different project results are shown here. The first (Nolazco and Whitley, 2023) examines wave conditions (i.e., A and U) under which beaches adjacent to an MN may show erosion. The second (Boutwell et al., 2024) examines the effects of changing the offshore wave height (H_0), which theoretically controls the total amount of wave energy approaching the shore, and the depth of closure (d_c ; see Figure 3b), which defines the beach area over which sediment is eroded and accreted (Ashton & Murray, 2006a; Slott et al., 2006). All these variables would be site-dependent for a real MN.

Results

Outcomes of the undergraduate research projects to date have been favorable, with over fifty students completing a research project. While undertaking a research project, students gain valuable experience in real-world scientific methodologies. Projects start with the formation of a robust scientific question, which is guided through discussions among research students and faculty mentors. This is followed by background research on the topic, generally through the

study of peer-reviewed research articles. This allows students to form hypotheses for their original questions and create a research plan on how to properly answer those questions.

Once this is complete, students have the opportunity to examine data on their project. This data can take various forms. For the Pandora Spectrometer Project, data is collected by the Pandora Spectrometer on campus as well as by other spectrometers in the Pandora Global Network. For the numerical modeling project, the data generally consists of model-produced shorelines that project how a hypothetical mega-nourishment (MN) on a beach may evolve. Students are expected to produce model results themselves by properly parameterizing and running various shoreline model simulations. Other data sets, such as offshore wave data (used to drive the numerical model), are available, but the analysis of such as not yet been necessary. Once data collection/production is complete, students are asked to analyze the data in the context of their research questions. These analyses are aided by Python and MATLAB scripts (some of which were written by the faculty mentors) that produce plots that are used in data analysis and sometimes used to examine specific metrics (e.g., the rate of shoreline retreat of a MN peninsula tip in the shoreline project case). These analyses can yield answers to the students' initial research questions, which act as conclusions to their project. These conclusions generally lead to other research questions that can be addressed by current or future students working in the SJC undergraduate research program.

Communication of research outcomes is also a key component of this program, as this skill is vital in any professional field. In most projects, students have the opportunity to give a poster presentation similar to one given at a professional conference (e.g., the American Geophysical Union Annual Meeting). The posters are then used to give a poster presentation at a symposium, usually the Undergraduate Research Symposium or the Honors Program

Symposium, both at the San Jacinto College South Campus. The poster presentation includes written elements (communication of the research on the poster) and oral elements where the students describe their work to the symposium audience.

SJC undergraduate research projects have also led to a large number of conference presentations, including those at the National Conference on Undergraduate Research (NCUR), the American Physical Society (APS) Global Physics Summit (e.g., Balch et al., 2021), and the Climate Start Agriculture Student Symposium at Texas A&M University Kingsville (e.g., Boutwell et al., 2024). Students have also had the opportunity to co-author peer-reviewed research articles through this initiative, examples of which are Gyawali et al. (2022), Gyawali et al. (2023), and Gyawali et al. (2025). Examples of student-produced research results for the two outlined projects can be found in Appendix A (Pandora Spectrometer Project) and Appendix B (Shoreline Modeling Project).

Case Context

The case context here involves undergraduate students at a two-year institution. The institution in question is the San Jacinto College (SJC) South Campus, one of the major campuses of the San Jacinto College District. This institution serves the metropolitan area of Houston, Texas, and provides educational resources for this community. The college is a Hispanic-serving institution with the majority of students seeking a two-year (associate) degree, a certificate, and/or transfer credit to a four-year institution (university). Most of the students who participate in this initiative are taking physical science courses (e.g., physics) and are likely pursuing a degree in the natural sciences or a STEM field. The majority of students in the program are also employed at least part-time, and many have a full academic load. Most have little to no understanding of how research is conducted at the university, graduate, or

professional level upon entry. This opportunity gives them real-world experience with advanced research, enhances their research skills, and offers them a strong experience to put on their resumes. Since this manuscript outlines work performed by undergraduate students participating in this initiative, and many helped author the manuscript, those students are listed as co-authors.

The current faculty mentors of this initiative are professors of physics at the college with Ph.D.'s in their respective subfields (i.e., atmospheric and ocean physics [oceanography]). SJC faculty are teaching-oriented, with 70% of their workload in this area. Unlike university faculty, SJC professors are not required to perform research, and doing so is not considered part of their required activities. Rather, the motivation behind the faculty to conduct research with students is to give undergraduates an experience similar to that of a graduate program, which is rare at two-year institutions. Such research experiences have been shown to be formative (Kuh, 2008) for undergraduates, which aligns well with the SJC faculty's primary goal of student success.

Discussion

Through this research experience, students are exposed to several practices that are often not found in common classroom environments. These include but are not limited to analysis of real in-situ data (e.g., Pandora spectrometer data), experience with modeled-produced data, experience with analysis programs and scripts (e.g., Python and MATLAB code designed for analysis of project data), and experience parameterizing models (i.e., CEM). Students are also instructed on scientific processes that are not generally found in curricula at the community-college level. For example, shoreline modeling students receive detailed instruction on sediment transport processes, wave physics, numerical modeling processes, and coastal engineering techniques (e.g., mega-nourishments) that are often only discussed at the graduate level. It is

also rare that undergraduate students in general have the opportunity to contribute to peer-reviewed journal articles, and offering such an opportunity in this initiative is distinctive.

Overall, these projects are aimed at giving undergraduate students an experience similar to a graduate research project, just on a smaller scale. The level of scientific research undertaken is on par with that of graduate-level studies. SJC research projects also include integral components to a graduate-level research experience, including the formation of research questions and hypotheses, the gathering or generation of scientific data, the analysis of that data, drawing conclusions from the analyses, and effectively communicating the results. It is necessary to maintain a relatively small scale for these undergraduate projects, as most projects are limited to one or two semesters, whereas graduate-level projects often run the course of multiple years. As such, the research questions are generally aimed at a specific detail in the overall situation. For example, an undergraduate MN shoreline modeling project may only examine the effects of one or two variables on MN evolution, where a graduate-level thesis would require a broader view.

There remain a number of obstacles to overcome in this initiative. Short student tenures continue to place limitations on the amount of time students have to work on research and the amount of time students can spend on their research. There has been discussion within the college administration to offer research as a dedicated course, though nothing has materialized at this time. Current plans are to continue this research initiative at the college with hopes of reaching a greater number of students. Future avenues of research may include combining efforts between the two programs by incorporating numerical modeling into the Pandora Spectrometer Project, though no models have yet been developed. Future undergraduate projects may also include the addition of a written thesis to complement their work.

Conclusions and Implications

The Pandora Spectrometer and Shoreline Modeling research projects are current initiatives at San Jacinto College, offering real-world research opportunities for undergraduates at a two-year institution. These initiatives are currently engaging students in the production of novel research, experience analyzing data (in situ and modeled), and presentation of their results. The initiative has resulted in over fifty poster presentations over the past seven years and has resulted in several peer-reviewed journal articles co-authored by participating undergraduates.

At San Jacinto College, this research initiative demonstrates how student research in advanced atmospheric monitoring and shoreline numerical modeling can be fully integrated into an educational environment. Looking ahead, expanding collaborations (e.g., linking Pandora data to larger climate studies) and supporting student-led projects will strengthen the impact of this work, building connections between education, community engagement, and scientific research.

AI Acknowledgement

No AI tools were used in the creation of this paper. The numerical model used is a physics-based process model and not considered generative AI. Grammarly was used to check grammar and spelling.

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Appendix A: Pandora Spectrometer Project Details

For this project, undergraduate students analyzed Pandora spectrometer retrievals of Nitrogen dioxide (NO_2) and Ozone (O_3). Both NO_2 and O_3 are toxic air pollutants that play a significant role in air quality and are associated with various respiratory and environmental health issues. They are also listed among the six “criteria” air pollutants regulated by the United States Environmental Protection Agency. NO_2 is a primary pollutant that is directly emitted into the atmosphere mainly from fuel combustion and other biomass-burning. It is also the precursor of O_3 . Unlike most air pollutants, O_3 forms due to other air pollutants released in the air, such as hydrocarbons and nitrogen oxides ($\text{NO}_x = \text{NO}_2 + \text{NO}$) from vehicles, refinery smokestacks, etc., especially during warm weather.

Results

Figures 4 and 5 present measurements from the San Jac Pandora spectrometer collected between January and June 2024 at San Jacinto College, Houston. The monthly averages (Fig. 4, right vertical axis) show clear seasonal behavior. Higher NO_2 concentrations in winter months due to increased fuel combustion for heating, stronger emissions from traffic during colder mornings, and frequent temperature inversions that trap pollutants closer to the earth’s surface. This boundary layer and less atmospheric mixing allow NO_2 to accumulate in the winter. In contrast to the summer, enhanced atmospheric mixing and faster photochemical reactions shorten the lifetime of NO_2 in the winter, leading to the lower concentrations as depicted in the plot. O_3 , shown on the left vertical axis of Figure 4, exhibits the opposite trend, peaking in late spring and summer when strong sunlight and higher temperatures promote photochemical formation. The drop in NO_2 , together with strong sunlight, leads to more ozone being produced, since NO_2 is a key ingredient in the photolysis that forms ozone.

Figure 4: Monthly averages of observed total (tropospheric plus stratospheric) vertical ozone (O₃) column and nitrogen dioxide (NO₂) surface concentration over Houston, TX.

Figure 5: The averaged box and whisker plots of the weekly average of the mean NO₂ (upper panel) and O₃ (lower panel) over Houston, TX.

Figure 5 shows box and whisker plots of the weekly averages for NO₂ (top panel) and O₃ (bottom panel). The boxes in the plot show the middle 50% of the data, the line inside the box

represents the median value, and the red dot represents the mean value. The two whiskers above and below the boxes show the range of measured data. From the data presented, weekly averages indicate higher NO_2 on weekdays compared to weekends, reflecting traffic and industrial activity. Conversely, O_3 can be higher on weekends, a well-known “weekend effect,” when reduced NO_x levels limit titration and allow more ozone accumulation.

Discussion

Monthly averages of San Jacinto College Pandora spectrometer data indicate that larger levels of NO_2 and O_3 are produced in the winter. This is likely linked to the higher usage of fuel combustion for heating, heavier morning traffic, and temperature inversions that trap NO_2 close to the ground. In the summer, NO_2 levels are reduced from stronger atmospheric mixing and photochemical reaction processes. O_3 levels show an opposite trend as they peak in the late spring and summer months. This is the result of increased sunlight and heat levels, which promote photochemical production of ozone. Furthermore, the diminished NO_2 levels in the summer also support ozone buildup.

Weekly averages of the Pandora data show that NO_2 levels are higher on weekdays, likely the result of increased traffic and industrial activity. NO_2 levels are the lowest on the weekends (i.e., Sundays) when said activity is diminished. Ozone levels are slightly higher on the weekends since lower NO emissions lead to less ozone being destroyed. Therefore, atmospheric conditions shift towards ozone formation rather than depletion. It is therefore likely that the spectrometer data is capturing both weekly changes (emission-driven) and seasonal changes (driven by weather and sunlight patterns).

Conclusions

The Pandora Spectrometer System at San Jacinto College is a valuable tool for monitoring nitrogen dioxide (NO₂) and ozone (O₃) through ground-based UV-VIS spectrometry. Connected to the Pandora Global Network and supported by NASA, the European Space Agency, and the Environmental Protection Agency, it enhances regional air quality observations and provides essential data for validating satellite measurements.

Results from the Houston site highlight the important role of NO₂ and O₃ in shaping local air quality and public health, reflecting both human activity and natural atmospheric processes. The continued use of Pandora instruments worldwide, particularly at colleges and universities, will be important for advancing our understanding of atmospheric chemistry and climate change. A key strength of the system is that, once installed, it requires little to no ongoing operational cost. This makes Pandora a cost-effective yet high-impact research platform. It also opens doors for students to gain hands-on experience by developing software tools, refining data analysis methods, and learning to interpret atmospheric processes. Their involvement can range from preparing poster presentations to contributing to peer-reviewed publications, providing authentic research experience that supports academic growth and career preparation.

Appendix B: Shoreline Modeling Project Details

Two shoreline projects simulating MN evolution were conducted from 2023 to 2024 (i.e., Nolzco and Whitley, 2023 and Boutwell et al., 2024). For both studies, a variety of wave climates (controlled by PDF variables A and U) are examined. A values ranged from 0.5 to 0.74, which would yield a 50% to 74% probability of waves approaching from the left of the domain, respectively. Sensitivity analyses showed that mirroring A values (e.g., $A = 0.25$ and 0.75) would yield coastlines that were mirror images of each other, so only one side of the A spectrum above 0.5 was examined. Sensitivity analyses also showed that the numerical instabilities would cause simulations with A values greater than 0.8 to break down, thus limiting the A range studied. U values from 0.0 to 0.4 were examined, showing a 0 to 40% change of high-angle waves approaching the shore ($\alpha_0 \geq 45^\circ$ relative to shore normal). These values were specifically identified via sensitivity analyses as wave climates where the MN experiences diffusion (spreading of sediment leading to a diminished cross-shore extension of the peninsula) rather than anti-diffusion, which leads to the removal of sediment in adjacent beaches to increase the MN peninsula's cross-shore extent. Since anti-diffusion undermines the purpose of an MN, only diffusional wave climates are examined (i.e., $U \leq 0.4$).

Results

Nolzco and Whitley (2023):

Here, the wave conditions under which erosion downdrift (adjacent to) an MN may occur on long time scales (e.g., 25 years) are examined. Model results showed that for $U = 0.0$ to 0.4 , no erosion was present on either side of an MN after 25 years of evolution (Figure 6a). This is true regardless of the A value used. For wave climates with $A = 0.75$ to 0.79 and $U = 0.0$, some erosion may begin to form downdrift (right) of the MN early in the simulations. This is due to a

reduction in wave energy on the right flank (resulting from shadow zones) and thus a reduction in sediment transport into beaches just to the right of the MN. These beaches still experience unreduced wave energy and therefore have unreduced sediment out of the region but reduced sediment into the region. This results in shoreline retreat in this area. However, for $A = 0.75$ to 0.79 and $U = 0.0$ simulations, the eroded areas begin to accrete within 5 to 8 years as the MN peninsula diffuses, and the shadow zones diminish. This decrease in MN cross-shore extent results in additional wave energy reaching the right flank of the MN, thus normalizing sediment transport into the eroding regions.

Figure 6. Modelled MN coastlines examining erosion patterns over 26 years. (a) shows a situation where an oblique wave climate is used ($A = .72$, 72% change of waves approaching from the left) and no high-angle waves ($U = 0$). Here, no shoreline retreat is present in the simulation. (b) shows an example where a highly oblique wave climate ($A = 0.73$) is coupled with a high probability (40% chance) of waves approaching from a high angle ($U = 0.4$). This

situation results in erosion downdrift (right) of the MN that persists throughout the 26-year simulation.

However, an increase in U can result in simulations where the eroded areas continuously erode without recovery (Figure 6b). For the wave climates studied, this occurs for high U values (i.e., $U = 0.4$, the maximum value tested) and highly oblique wave climates ($A = 0.71$ to 0.79). This gives the MN right flank the highest chance of being in a shadow zone and thus is unable to transport sediment to beaches just downdrift (right) of the MN. Even though the MN diffuses, the eroded region's shoreline continues to retreat to the point where it remains within a shadow zone regardless of the MN tip's position. It is therefore consistently undergoing erosion, and shoreline retreat persists throughout the 26 years of simulation.

Boutwell et al. (2024):

Here, the effects of a changing offshore wave height (H_0) and depth of closure (d_c) are examined (Figure 7). The values of H_0 and d_c remain fixed throughout a single simulation, though they are altered from simulation to simulation. In general, an increase in H_0 (e.g., 0.5 m to 1.0 m) results in faster diffusion of the MN, regardless of the wave angle spectrum. This makes sense considering the wave height is directly proportional to the wave energy. An increase in the amount of wave energy delivered to a shoreline results in an increase in sediment transport, and thus, shoreline dynamics evolve more quickly. Increasing the depth of closure in the model (e.g., from 4 m to 8 m) results in a reduced diffusion rate with transport occurring less quickly. This occurs because volumetric transport fluxes (Q_s) are unaffected by d_c . However, the change in the fractional amount of sediment in each cell per time step (ΔF), calculated by (2), is inversely proportional to d_c . This results in a decrease in shoreline change per time step Q_s values being equal.

Figure 7. Effects of altering (a) offshore wave height (H_0) and (b) the depth of closure (d_c) on MN evolution. In general, H_0 and sediment transport rates (Q_s) are directly proportional. Thus, an increase in H_0 results in faster morphology. d_c , however, is inversely proportional to coastline changes via (2), and higher d_c values therefore result in slower morphology.

Discussion

For the shoreline modeling project, the results have implications regarding the construction of potential mega-nourishments (MNs). Given the modeled erosion patterns observed in certain simulations, it would not be advisable to construct an MN on a site possessing a highly oblique wave climate with a high probability of waves coming from relatively the same direction and a relatively high probability of high-angle waves, at least for MNs with aspect parameters similar to those modeled. Models indicate potential risk for persistent erosion patterns downdrift of an MN under such wave conditions. Models also show a strong correlation between MN diffusion rates and both offshore wave height and the site's depth of closure (directly and indirectly proportional, respectively). High diffusion rates may be desirable for such a project, as it cuts

down on potential project time (e.g., the MN in the Netherlands had a 15+ year project lifespan), but increasing overall transport levels may have other implications. It should be noted that previous modeling efforts implied that MNs may have a faster transport rate than traditional nourishments (Whitley et al., 2021). Furthermore, it is important to note that the model used (CEM) does not incorporate known beach processes such as cross-shore transport (e.g., aeolian). These processes were observed to be present at the Sand Engine in the Netherlands (de Schipper et al., 2016), and some sediment transported was lost to the system (e.g., transported offshore). This raises efficiency questions with regard to nourishment projects such as MNs. *Conclusions:*

The Coastline Evolution Model is also a useful tool for students to investigate the implications of mega-nourishment (MN) on beaches and explore hypothetical scenarios for them. Student research to this point shows that modeled MNs under highly oblique wave conditions (high probability of coming from the same general direction and at a relatively high angle) produce areas of erosion adjacent to an MN that result from sediment starvation (less sediment transport into an area) arising from wave shadow zones. Modeling efforts have also shown a directly proportional relationship between offshore wave height and transport rates (and thus MN diffusion rate) and an inverse relationship between depth of closure and MN diffusion rate.